

THE MOUNTAIN PRODUCT IN THE CONTEXT OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT – TRENDS AND PERSPECTIVES IN THE POST-PANDEMIC PERIOD

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Abstract

The “Mountain Product” has become a reality of sustainable development. The quality term offers recognition for the quality of these products and new opportunities for the producers, as well as for the consumers. Most of the consumers already associate the term “mountain” with the idea of health, authenticity, purity and quality. This has been brought forward even more by the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic that has taken over our country from the beginning of 2020. The population has opted for a healthy diet, the mountain products becoming highly sought for. The general public has become more interested by healthy diets, and the mountain products have become very much sought after. The future of the socio-economic development of the mountain area must be looked at in the context of stabilizing the local population, of a superior valorification of the raw materials, preserving cultural identity, protecting the environment, all of them premises that will ensure an upward evolution of mountain communities. The presence of the logo “mountain product” on the labels of the products that have been granted the right to use the term helps promote the territories these products are coming from. Through their identity elements, combined with the images on the product label, the consumer can associate the taste of the products with the landscapes, customs and traditions of the area they are coming from.

Keywords: *mountain product, mountain, producer, health, pandemic.*

INTRODUCTION

The quality term “mountain product” has been established as an optional quality term and is assigned to products intended for human consumption, produced from raw materials, but also for which the livestock feed originates mainly in the mountain area, while the processed products are also processed in the mountain area (R. UE nr. 1305, 2013; R. UE nr. 1151, 2012; R. UE nr. 665, 2012).

In Romania, the National Mountain Area Agency is the institution issuing the decisions to grant the rights to use the optional quality term “Mountain product” according to the provisions of Order no. 174/20.07.2021 with regards to the approval of the Procedure of verification of conformity of the data in the tender for the right to use the quality term “mountain product” and for the control to verify the compliance with European and national legislation by the economic operators that have been granted the right to use the aforementioned quality term (Hotărârea nr. 506, 2016).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research methods employed in this work are: the method of analysis of statistic indicators, the method of comparative analysis and the method of bibliographic analysis.

The analysis material comes from specialty publications, national statistics and includes statistical data processed from specialized websites.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The main resource for the socio-economic development of the mountain area is represented by products “from the mountain”. In the context of the ongoing evolution of the coronavirus pandemic and taking into account the rising numbers of registered mountain products, we can see the “mountain product” policy is starting to bear fruit for the producers and/or processors, as well as for the consumers that are oriented towards consuming healthy products, some of them even from the farm’s door.

When the pandemic settled in, more and more young persons working abroad have returned “home” and, taking advantage of the experience aquired working there, once back in the country they have invested their resources in developing the existing family farms, understanding the importance of natural products consumption, but especially the importance of being independent from an economical point of view.

One of the present problems confronting the population in the mountain area is the lack of conditions to process raw materials at farm level, which leads to a low price for the production and that is a destabilising factor, affecting the viability of the farms in the area.

The intrinsic value of the agricultural primary products produced in the mountain area stands out through quality and taste, as these are food products with very high value, they are healthy (sanogenic even), pollutant-free and uncontaminated, produced through “clean”, extensive, traditional agricultural practices, with high work and time investment needed to produce them, originating from livestock living in a clean, free and quiet environment, blessed by solar energy, water, air and feed of the highest quality, from high natural value pastures.

Taking all these factors into account, the agricultural products from the mountain area should be priced accordingly, seriously competing even with eco products.

The mountain village is economically centered around the integrated peasant household. The household is a living, resting, working place. The peasant household is an integrated structure, with the various functions under its roof compatible and complementary. Taking into account the size and complexity, the working spirit of the family, each area has its distinct particularities, even if these are conceptually close. The households ensure the preservation and perpetuation of the traditional village space.

The clean, safe, sustainable environment represents a guarantee for the quality of life and for the opportunities to develop various forms of economic activities, agriculture and tourism in particular.

Out of all the problems that need solving, a priority is approaching the migration of workforce by attracting young people to the mountain area. This should also be tackled by supporting investments in the non-agricultural activities, making life in the rural mountain area attractive.

Romania needs to have a careful, intelligent approach about its resources, and to aim for European level results. We have to bring Europe and Romania to the reality of the mountain area and to use the advantages offered by this area. One of them is the preservation of the mountains cultural heritage, which is part of our national identity.

Once the legislation concerning the “mountain product” has been implemented, the subject has attracted the attention of the researchers.

The optional quality term “mountain product” is addressed to products for human consumption, in which: the raw materials, but also the fodder for farm animals, originates mainly from mountain areas, and in the case of processed products, the processing is also done in the mountain area (Onesifereanu, 2018).

The ecological quality of farm food, of animal or vegetable origin, is clearly superior to those similar to the plain areas (Ungureanu și Gițan, 2020). The National Mountain Area Agency is supporting the farmers with the legislative framework updated according to the evolution of the economical status at national level, the demand from the consumers and the needs of the farmers for sustainable productions.

The visual identity element of the products that have been granted the right to use the optional quality term “Mountain product” is the logo “Mountain Product” (Fig. 1), and that is why all the products that have been granted the right to use the term have this logo on their labels (OM nr. 174, 2021; AZM; MADR).

Fig.1. The “Mountain Product” logo

Source: National Agency for Mountain Area

Using the term “Mountain product” on the label offers recognition for these products and a new opportunity for the producers, as well as for the consumers. This idea has been highlighted even more by the effects of the COVID 19 pandemic in our country, from the beginning of 2020.

A large part of the producers from the counties Bistrița Năsăud, Harghita, Covasna and Brașov that have individually registered products from this category in the National Registry of the Mountain Products, are now trying to find ways to associate in various forms. This is a welcome trend, because once they reach the high volume market, the shelves of the large retailers, the producers are guaranteed the sale of their products, and the consumers will be able to enjoy them.

The range of products registered in the National Register of Mountain Products is varied. There are products of plant and animal origin, both processed and unprocessed. Obtaining unprocessed products and placing them on the market by manufacturers only makes them capitalize on them and provide quality to customers, but the added value is brought by the processed products. Until August of 2021, they were present in the National

Register of Mountain Products in a percentage of 30%. Those products come from the processing of milk, meat, fruit and vegetables (Diagram no. 1) (AZM).

The use of the logo on the mountain products makes them easily recognizable by the consumers of high value, superior quality food products, consumers that also want to be certain that standards are being followed. The product label assures the consumer the biological quality and the sanitary-veterinary safety of the products are guaranteed, which will determine an increase in demand for such products.

The products with added value, the products registered in the National Registry of the Mountain products respectively, can contribute to the sustainable economic growth both on the domestic market and abroad.

Categoriile de produse ce au dobândit dreptul de utilizare a mențiunii de calitate facultative "produs montan" % ocupat de produse organizate pe categorii N° total = 2551

Diagram no. 1

Source: the authors – 2021

Trends and perspectives in the post-pandemic period

The COVID 19 crisis puts us in a position where we need to rethink our collective way of living. The start of the COVID 19 pandemic in 2020 has brought people worldwide in a situation most of them never experienced before in their lifetimes.

The economic crisis generated by the COVID 19 pandemic had a significant impact on the national economy, affecting fields like agriculture and tourism. The uncertainty generated by the evolution of the pandemic in the coming months will lead to an accelerated decrease in investments, a return to the previous dynamic of economic growth being expected only by 2025. It is recognized that tourism associated with rural resources and traditional products is an important "tool" for the revitalization of the rural economy and is an essential component of the local development strategy (Ungureanu și Gițan, 2020).

The effects of the pandemic are changing our lives considerably, determining a need to adapt to new conditions of life and work.

The worrying statistics on the impact of the diseases caused by unhealthy diets, as well as the need to raise productivity and economic efficiency, have determined the Government to lower the VAT percentage from 9% to 5 % on the high quality, eco, traditional and mountain products, (EGD no. 31 of 14 May 2019). This only applies to products authorized by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development and delivered inside Romania.

Mountain product: Trends and perspectives in the post-pandemic period

Analysing the data in the National Registry for the Mountain Products, a public document of interest for the producers, as well as for the consumers, the number of products that have been granted the right to use the optional quality term "mountain product" has been rising considerably since the coronavirus pandemic started.

If, by 31.12.2019, there were 454 products registered with 119 decisions granted, by the end of 2020 there were 1,540 products registered with 491 decisions, nearly three times more. Since beginning 2021 until 31 August 2021 another 1,011 products have been registered that have been granted the right to use the quality term through 391 decisions (diagram no. 2) (AZM).

Diagram no. 2

Source: the author – 2021

There is an ascending trend for the number registered or pending registration in the National Registry of the Mountain Products. This is due to the rising demand on the market for healthy products, as well as of the interest of the producers and processors of mountain products to certify their products with ease, their quality justified basen on a simplified documentation.

The mountain product means:

- OPPORTUNITY – For the producer and/or processor, because of the straightforward procedure to be granted the right to use the quality term, and the facilities they receive regardless of the legal registration form.

The logo helps large retailers build confidence, in order to accept the product on their shelves.

- **NECESSITY** – For the consumer, because the products are of clearly higher quality. The products with added value, the products registered in the NRMP respectively, have significantly lower numbers, approx. 30% of the total mountain products. The ecological quality of farm food, of animal or vegetable origin, is clearly superior to those similar to the plain areas. The lack of chemicalization in the mountain area and the use of only organic fertilizers is the guarantor of this quality. In addition, the forest's accessory products can be added: berries (blueberries, raspberries, blackberries, strawberries, cranberries), edible mushrooms, medicinal plants from spontaneous flora. All this, being true sources of health. They can be certified as "mountain products", thus increasing their value (Ungureanu și Gițan, 2020).

CONCLUSIONS

Local producers already understood the importance of preserving the traditional ways to produce food for their families and other locals, or for tourists seeking to sample the famed "food with taste". The products are fresh, of a quality that cannot be found on the shelves of regular stores.

Family farms in the mountain area are an essential contributing factor to the food security, and the diversity of the products that have received the right to use the optional quality term "mountain product" covers the food intake necessities of the consumers.

Animal breeding in the mountain area is a century-old activity due to mountain relief, with natural grasslands and hayfields, with a rich flora and climate proper for this activity. Animal breeding activity is inherited from ancient times, the local community preserving many customs, including those relating to the traditionalism of products, among them the dairy products (Bocănici și Cristea, 2014).

The "Mountain product", for the consumer, can be seen as a "breath of oxygen", a return to the taste of home, offering a piece of tranquility and interior joy in these uncertain times.

As far as markets are concerned, solutions need to be found to stabilize short supply chains (the delivery from a mountain farmer to the consumer involving as low a number of intermediaries as possible), thus ensuring stability and decent living for the mountain farmers.

REFERENCES

- Bocănici, M., Cristea, S.** 2014. Obținerea produselor lactate prin metode tradiționale de procesare a laptelui de oaie în zona montană, pe Valea Troțușului, în România., Lucrare publicată în Volumul 185 din Congresul European de Biotehnologie, Lecce.
- Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 665/2014** of 11 March 2014 supplementing Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to conditions of use of the optional quality term 'mountain product'.
- Emergency government ordinance no. 3/2015** for the approval of payment schemes applied in agriculture in the period 2015–2020 and to amend art. 2 of Law no. 36/1991 with regards to agricultural enterprises and other associative forms in agriculture.
- Government Decision no. 506 of 20 July 2016** with regards to the institutional framework and certain measures do apply Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 665/2014 of

11 March 2014 supplementing Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to conditions of use of the optional quality term “mountain product”.

<http://www.azm.gov.ro>

<http://www.madr.ro>

Law no. 197/2018. The mountain law.

Mountain Area Agency. Best practices guide on granting the right to use the optional quality term ,mountain product.

Onesifereanu, N., Ștefan, G., Gițan, D. 2018. Produsul montan în ecuația economiilor locale, *Lucrări Științifice* – vol. 61(2)/2018, seria Agronomie – Universitatea de Științe Agricole și Medicină Veterinară Iași.

Order of the minister of agriculture and rural development no. 174 of 20 July 2021 with regards to the Procedure of conformity verification for the tada in the tender books submitted for the right to use the optional quality term “mountain product” and for the control to verify the compliance with the European and national legislation by the economic operators that have been granted the right to use the aforementioned term.

Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 November 2012 on quality schemes for agricultural products and foodstuffs.

Regulation (EU) No 1305/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 on support for rural development by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 1698/2005.

Rey R. 2013. Multianual Strategy for the Romanian Carpathians – HORIZON 2040, Terra Nostra Publishing House, Iași, 2013.

Rey R. 2014. The mountains and the 21st century. Comparative study of European strategies for the mountain areas with specific reference to the Romanian Carpathians. The M1 – SEE Plan, Electra Publishing House (ICPE).

Ștefan, G. 2006. Economics and agri-food politics, ALFA Publishing House, Iași.

Ungureanu, D., Gițan, D. 2020, Evaluarea potențialului agro-turistic în zona montană a României. Starea de lucruri și noile provocări, ESPERA, București.